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**EDUCATION BETWEEN TRADITION
AND MODERNITY**

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**IS THE USE OF WEB 2.0 TECHNOLOGY POSSIBLE IN LEARNING?
(Preview of a Pilot Study on the Use of Modern Information and Communication
Technology in High School)**

Abstract:

The research objectives were to register the level and purpose of different possibilities of the Internet and its content for young people, and to determine the attitudes of young people towards the possibilities of implementing them in education and learning. The assumption of the research was based on the fact that ICT is effectively used in the classroom and that the student's usage of it is in correlation with successful learning outcomes. To obtain the data, the subjects were interviewed through a questionnaire that had been specifically designed for this study. A total of 87 students of Medical School were surveyed, and out of them 27 were from the first year, 28 from the second year, and 32 from the third year. Although the main motivation in using Web 2.0 tools is to exchange entertainment content, music and pictures, the results showed that students believe that it is possible to use the Internet in the learning process. On average, students use the most popular Web 2.0 social networking tools 1, 2 or 3 hours a day. The most popular social network is Facebook. For the purpose of learning, most students use Wiki pages (such as Wikipedia), especially for homework, writing papers or finding out information about celebrities. These results highlight the importance of monitoring the use of Web 2.0 tools for young people and the introduction of the Internet in the school, as well as provide a basis for further similar studies.

Key words: INTERNET, WEB 2.0 TECHNOLOGY, SOCIAL NETWORKING, BLOG.

1. Introduction

One of the biggest and most visible consequences of the changes due to the very rapid development of Information and Communication Technology in the last decade is the need for thorough change of the education system. The young generations were born and

grew up surrounded by computers, video games, digital music players and mobile phones, and are using them skillfully as they form an integral part of their lives. As a result, in their thinking patterns, unlike the previous generations of scholars, they receive and process information very quickly, they can do more tasks at the same time, they prefer a graphical representation of the text, and prefer games to serious work and study. Besides this, they expect immediate reward or feedback and work best when they are connected.

Today, the availability of a multitude of information is achieved primarily through the Internet as a global system of links between computers, which allows people to communicate with each other and come to different information on the global World Wide Web, or WWW. An individual who accesses the Internet is engaged in important decision-making about where to access the web page, what information to collect, how to evaluate it, and how to continue to use it (Danilovikj, 2004).

While many teachers and educators would use these facts as arguments against ICT, the point is that this has to be faced and examined, not just in terms of methods and techniques of teaching, but also regarding the curriculum of education. The needs of the school have always been relevant and have remained current. According to this, it is necessary to continually monitor ITC novelties and meet the needs of the social environment. That implies the reasons of continuous testing, revising and modernizing the teaching curriculum, the teaching methods, forms and techniques.

There is a view that the skills of information operation, which is the essence of information literacy can be developed during training, and designed so that development occurs through the content and activities of different subjects and topics (Lazarevikj, 2007).

A student who has mastered information literacy possesses the following skills (Shrock, 2003, in Lazarevikj, 2007):

1. Assesses the information effectively and efficiently:
 - Is aware of the need for information,
 - Formulates questions that need to obtain sought-after information,
 - Identifies various potential sources of information.
2. Evaluates information critically and competently:
 - Determines the accuracy and relevance,
 - Distinguishes facts, points of view, opinions,
 - Identifies inaccurate information that may be misleading (deceiving),
 - Selects information according to the problem or issue in mind.
3. Uses information effectively and creatively:
 - Organizes information for practical application,
 - Uses information in critical thinking and problem-solving,
 - Produces and sends (passes on) information in the proper format.

2. *Web 2.0 Technology*

The term “Web 2.0” is associated with web applications that facilitate participatory information through sharing, interoperability, user-centered design, and collaboration on the World Wide Web. The term “information sharing” in the information technology lexicon has a long history. Traditional information-sharing is referred to as one-to-one exchanges of data between a sender and receiver. From the computer scientist’s point of view, the four primary information-sharing design patterns are: sharing information one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-many, and many-to-one. Interoperability means how to work together (interoperate). The user-centered design is a design philosophy and a process in which needs, wants and limitations of the product’s end users are paid extensive attention to at each stage of the design process (www.2.cs.cmu.edu).

Web 2.0 technology allows users to interact and collaborate with each other in a social media dialogue as creators prosumers³² of user-generated content in a virtual community, in contrast to websites where users as consumers are limited to the passive viewing of the content that was created for them. Examples of Web 2.0 include social networking sites, blogs, wikis, video sharing sites, hosted services, web applications, mishaps and folksonomies.

An important part of Web 2.0 is the social Web, which is a fundamental shift in the way in which people communicate. The social web consists of a number of online tools and platforms where people share their perspectives, opinions, thoughts and experiences. Web 2.0 applications tend to interact much more with the end user. As such, the end user is not only the user of the application, but also the participant. Some of the Web 2.0 tools are: (eobrazovanje.wordpress.com):

Podcasting - A podcast is an audio or video file recorded and used to deliver information to remote audiences via the Internet.

Blogging - A blog is a website that allows users to reflect, share opinions, and discuss various topics in the form of an online journal while readers may comment on posts. Most blogs are written in a slightly informal tone (personal journals, news, businesses, etc.)

Contributing to RSS - A web publishing technology that allows end users to automatically receive new digital content from the provider. Originally used for text files, RSS is now also used to deliver audio and video content.

Social bookmarking - A method for Internet users to share, organize, search and manage bookmarks of web resources. Unlike file sharing, the resources themselves aren’t shared, but the bookmarks merely reference them.

Social networking - The interaction between a group of people who share a common interest (such as Facebook or Twitter).

³² *Prosumer* is formed by contracting either the word *professional* or *producer* with the word *consumer*. The term has taken on multiple meanings: the business sector sees the prosumer (professional–consumer) as a market segment, whereas economists see the prosumer (producer–consumer) as having greater independence from the mainstream economy.

3. Web 2.0 And learning

Considering the positive aspects of Web 2.0 technology that were presented in the previous part of this work, it is hardly surprising that Web 2.0 tools have quickly found their place in education. Now the students can engage in the process of preparing and presenting the material and the content of the lessons, and can communicate with their teachers and other students within the group. Blogs, wiki pages, podcasts and social networks quickly capture youngsters, because now the focus shifts from content to students and their communication and cooperation that is becoming a very important factor.

Peer learning is very effective because it is the best way to learn something if you are preparing material for teaching somebody else. Students become teachers, i.e. they become specialized in certain areas, ask questions and give each other answers, help each other to understand what they have already understood. This procedure is in the theory of pedagogy known as the highest level of learning, which implies the permanence of the acquired knowledge (Shevkushikj-Mandikj, 2003).

Nick Peachey (www.scribd.com) in his electronic publication about Web 2.0 tools (Peachey, 2009) said that the advantages of using this technology in school are numerous, and that Web 2.0 enhanced the learning potential of the web. Web 2.0 enables:

Socialization - Through socialization our students can use the language and skills they are learning to build networks and develop relationships with real people.

Collaboration - They can work together with others to construct and share real knowledge.

Creativity - They can create genuine products, in a wide range and combination of media to high standards, that will have a real audience.

Authenticity - The tasks and activities they do and the people they communicate with are real and motivating.

Sharing - They can share what they create and learn with and from each other.

In this work, we would like to highlight the usage of the Web 2.0. Is it possible to use Web 2.0 technology and peer relationship for learning purposes? Do our students really use the Internet, especially Web 2.0 technologies, in order to acquire new knowledge?

4. Aim

The aim of this study is to register the degree and purpose of using different possibilities of the Internet by young people in high school and to identify the attitudes of young people about the possibilities of applying them in education and learning. The assumption of our research was based on the effective use of ICT in the classroom and students using Web 2.0 becoming teacher-experts in specific areas correlated with successful learning outcomes.

5. Research methods

Respondents: In the research, a total of 87 students of Medical School were surveyed: 27 were students from the first year, 28 from the second year, and 32 from the third year.

Instruments and procedures: To obtain the data, the subjects were surveyed by an anonymous questionnaire, which was specifically designed for this study. The questionnaire used in the survey contained a total of 13 open-ended and multiple-choice questions.

Statistical analysis: The data was processed by the software package “Statistica 9.1 for Windows”. Descriptive statistics and data analysis was employed for the statistical analysis.

6. Results and discussion

* Note: Not all students answered all the questions and because of that it is possible for there to be a discrepancy between the number of respondents in this sample and the number described in relation to the individual questions.

The assumption of the study was based on the fact that ICT is effectively used in the classroom and that students using Web 2.0 become teacher-experts in specific areas. However, successful learning outcomes on the basis of these results have not been confirmed. The first observation after processing the results of the study was that out of the 87 students interviewed, nobody said that through Web 2.0 tools they engage in exchange of instructional content, or any other content applicable to learning.

The results show that 86 students from the 87 use the Internet. However, the purpose of using the Internet is different. From the descriptive responses 5 categories of responses that describe the purpose of using the Internet could be sorted out. From Table 1 we can see categories of responses and the total number of specific responses in relation to class participants.

Table 1. The purpose of using the Internet

Grade/Purpose	Entertainment	Learning	Information	Contacts	Miscellaneous
1	26	18	2	14	5
2	23	19	3	2	1
3	20	12	3	2	1
All	69	49	8	14	7

Analysis of the data shows that there are only four students who do not have any Internet profile on the Internet networking sites Facebook and MySpace. 77 students use one of these two sites, while 6 have a profile on both social networks. It is noticeable that there is a significant preference of the network of Facebook.

Young people spend much time using the Internet social networks. As many as 10 pupils say that they use social networking more than 5 hours during the day. 42 students said that they spend a maximum of 1 hour a day for the use of these networks, while 23 students used Facebook or MySpace from 1 to 3 hours a day. Two students gave a vague answer. These social networks are most commonly used to exchange information (58 respondents) and to exchange music and pictures (31 respondents). However, 53 students reported that social networking helped them in learning, while others have no such experience. In relation to the school, according to our respondents, social networks enable sharing of information in the form and terms according to the demands of the teachers. Communication for this purpose takes place in closed Internet groups.

A small number of young people are members of a forum, and an even smaller number of students have their own blog, which is not the case in relation to the use of chats (Table 2). A blog, as a web space where users share their opinion with others, discuss different issues, and where readers can comment on posted content, according to the data of the study, is characterized as a tool that is used the least.

Table 2. The use of chats, forums, blogs

	Own blog	Forum member	Chat
Uses	2	14	69
Doesn't use	83	73	14

The respondents used chats for a variety of purposes: 63 respondents stated that they used chats for the purpose of socializing and chatting with friends, 4 respondents said the purpose was obtaining urgent and important information, while 3 of them said that they use chats for correspondence with potential romantic partners.

70 respondents answered that they are using Wiki pages, however other respondents do not use this Internet encyclopedia. The most common reasons are lack of confidence in the Internet or the validity of the content placed on Wiki pages. When using Wiki pages it is usually for the purpose of studying, doing homework or writing papers (63 students), while 8 students use Wiki pages for finding out information about celebrities or others.

29 subjects have YouTube accounts, while 58 of them declared that they do not have an account. 70 respondents visit this site and use it solely for listening to music, or watching videos and clips. Only 17 respondents used this program for educational purposes, and only two for the purpose of learning about the school curriculum.

This study, whose data were interpreted, is a pilot study, and the results obtained have the character of working material for further and broader research. It is evident that the information and communications tools are increasingly used in learning and education, but we can see that there is great need for referring to technology and teaching students how to use the Internet and Web 2.0 tools for better learning and performing tasks related to their school obligations. The research interests and motivation of students in connection

with the use of Web 2.0 tools and the Internet in general, are not in the domain of teaching curriculum content. For this reason, we sense that in the near future there will be a need for another extensive research on this subject which would provide more specific information to precisely define the steps in teaching students.

References

- Danilovikj, M. (2004). Hipermedijalna interaktivna obrazovna tehnologija i učenje; Znanje i postignuće. Beograd: Insitut za pedagoška istraživanja.
- Kennewell, S., Parkinson, J., & Tanner, H. (2000). Developing the ICT Capable School. London: Routledge Falmer.
- Lazarevikj, D. (2007). Obrazovanje mladih za korišćenje informacija sa interneta - oslonci u razvoju kritičkog mišljenja, In Nastava i vaspitanje, vol. 2.
- Peachey, N. (2009). Web 2.0 Tools for Teachers
<<http://www.scribd.com/doc/19576895/Web-20-Tools-for-Teachers>>
- Shevkushikj-Mandikj, S. G. (2003). Kreiranje uslova za kooperativno učenje: osnovni elementi, In Zbornik Instituta za pedagoška istraživanja, vol. 35 (pp. 94-110).
<<http://scindeks.nb.rs>>
<www.eobrazovanje.wordpress.com/2009/04/18/web-20-tehnologije/#comment-3>
<<http://prezi.com/zaowmwfqi5fa/web-20-and-social-media-for-school-districts>>
<<http://www.2.cs.cmu.edu/~kiesler/publications/1994pdfs/1994Constant-WhatsMine.pdf>>

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ДАЛИ Е МОЖНА УПОТРЕБАТА НА 2.0 ТЕХНОЛОГИЈАТА ВО УЧЕЊЕТО? (РАЗГЛЕДУВАЊЕ НА ПИЛОТ-СТУДИЈА ЗА УПОТРЕБАТА НА СОВРЕМЕНА ИНФОРМАЦИСКА И КОМУНИКАЦИСКА ТЕХНОЛОГИЈА ВО СРЕДНИТЕ УЧИЛИШТА)

Апстракт

Истражувачките цели се однесуваат на забележување на степенот и целите на различните можности на интернетот и неговите содржини за младите луѓе, како и одредување на ставовите на младите луѓе кон можностите за нивно имплементирање во образованието и учењето. Претпоставката на истражувањето е базирана врз фактот што ИКТ ефикасно се користи во наставата и дека нејзината употреба е во тесна корелација со исходот од успешно учење. За да се дојде до податоци, испитаниците беа интервјуирани преку прашалник кој беше специјално склопен за ова истражување. Во анкетата учествуваа вкупно 87 студенти од медицинско училиште, односно 27 од нив беа од прва година, 28 беа од втора година, и 32 беа од трета година. Иако главната мотивација при употребата на 2.0 алатките е за размена на забавни содржини, музика и слики, сепак резултатите покажаа дека учениците веруваат дека е можно да се искористи интернетот во процесот на учење. Учениците ги користат најпопуларните 2.0 алатки за социјално вмрежување во просек 1, 2 или 3 часа на ден, а најпопуларната социјална мрежа е Фејсбук. За целите на учење, повеќето ученици користат вики-страници (како Википедија), особено за домашни работи, пишување семинарски работи или за изнаоѓање информации за славни личности. Овие информации ја нагласуваат важноста на набљудување на употребата на 2.0 алатките за младите луѓе и за воведување на интернетот во училиштето, како и за создавање на основа за други слични истражувања.

Клучни зборови: ИНТЕРНЕТ, 2.0. ТЕХНОЛОГИЈА, СОЦИЈАЛНО ВМРЕЖУВАЊЕ, БЛОГ.